

THE INEXTRICABLE LINK BETWEEN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND THE LABOR MARKET

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the relevance of the relationship between the vocational education system and the labor market, their role in economic and social development. The article substantiates the ways to adapt vocational education to the labor market, ensure youth employment, and achieve economic efficiency.*

Keywords: *the labor market, main factors, practice-oriented, Technological innovation, Flexible and modular curricula, Soft skills, Certification and international standards, dual education.*

INTRODUCTION

In the modern era, one of the main factors of the development of any country is qualified, professional human resources. In particular, one of the most important directions of economic and social development is the creation of a vocational education system that trains personnel who meet market requirements and are ready for work. Through this system, all segments of society will have the opportunity to learn a profession, the unemployment rate will decrease, and young people will have real conditions to demonstrate their potential.

METHODOLOGY

Large-scale reforms are being implemented in the field of vocational education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, starting from 2020, professional educational institutions have been reorganized on the basis of a new system, and vocational schools, colleges and technical schools have been launched. Their main task is to provide education integrated with production in accordance with modern technologies, and to create conditions for the preparation of young people for independent labor activity.

DISCUSSION

Today's labor market is constantly changing. New professions are emerging, and the demand for existing professions is changing under the influence of various factors. Therefore, the vocational education system must be flexible to the real requirements of the labor market. After all, specialists who have a profession, understand the requirements of production, and are able to master modern technology are the backbone of economic development.

The inextricable link between vocational education and the labor market is a reciprocal, two-way process, in which the education system trains the necessary specialists for the labor market, and the labor market determines what personnel are needed for education. If there is no balance in this relationship, problems such as personnel shortages, unemployment, and social instability arise in the labor market.

Today, strong changes are taking place in education systems around the world. New technologies, changing labor market needs, and increasing demand for human capital are also directly affecting the vocational education system. It is for this reason that vocational education is

focused on training specialists who can meet the requirements of today, possessing modern knowledge and skills. Vocational education is not just a system that provides theoretical knowledge, but also a process that forms practical skills and qualifications, preparing young people for independent labor activity. The most important requirement of a modern vocational education system is the organization of education integrated with production, that is, brought closer to real working conditions. Currently, special attention is paid to vocational education in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Starting from 2020, the activities of vocational schools, colleges and technical schools have been resumed. These institutions: specialized programs for acquiring working professions have been developed; Work has begun on providing modern technical facilities and equipment; curricula and programs are being improved with the participation of employers; the number of hours allocated to practical training is being increased. The modern model of vocational education emphasizes the following key requirements:

1- table.

1. Practice-oriented

The educational process should not take place only in classrooms. Through practical work, internships, and training, students will get acquainted with the real aspects of their profession. This will help them adapt to work faster and operate effectively.

2. Technological innovation

Today's professions are based on high technology. For example, modern computers, software, and laboratories are needed to study in areas such as automation, IT, electrical engineering, robotics, graphic design, and 3D modeling. Without this infrastructure, the student is not ready for the real labor market.

3. Flexible and modular curricula

Modern vocational education should be organized on the basis of modular programs, taking into account the personal needs of students and the needs of the labor market. This allows the student to be trained in a specific area in a short time.

4. Soft skills – focus on “soft skills”

Modern employers pay great attention not only to technical knowledge, but also to skills such as teamwork, communication, problem solving, critical thinking, and flexibility. Therefore, vocational education institutions are now trying to form a system for teaching these skills.

5. Certification and international standards

The graduate should not only be awarded a diploma, but also have a national or international certificate proving his level of qualification. This will help him to be competitive in the labor market. For example, there are internationally recognized certificates in such fields as IT, tailoring, and electrical engineering.

The economic stability and social development of any country depend, first of all, on the proper formation of the labor market and the provision of a qualified workforce. The labor market is a system formed on the basis of mutual supply and demand between employers and job seekers. The presence of competitive, modern professional skills in this system determines the country's production potential. In this regard, vocational education institutions are considered the main institution that directly serves the needs of the labor market.

The following main factors contribute to the imbalance of personnel:

1. Poor labor market forecasts.
2. Outdated curricula.
3. Weak cooperation with employers.
4. Wrong career choices of young people.

Integrating vocational education with production is one of the most important directions for increasing the effectiveness of vocational education today. The experience of developed countries shows that an education system combined with practice significantly increases the adaptability of graduates to the labor market. In particular, the dual education model is recognized as the most successful and promising approach in this regard.

2- table.

The inextricable link between vocational education and the labor market is an important factor that directly affects the economic development, employment rate and social stability of each country. Today, the training of competitive, innovative thinking and practical skills has become

the main task of the education system. This requires the direct integration of vocational education with the labor market.

The experience of Uzbekistan shows that significant results are being achieved through the reforms carried out in vocational schools, technical schools and colleges, including the introduction of a dual education model, strengthening cooperation with production, and the formation of curricula appropriate to modern professions and areas. However, there are still a number of problems in this regard: the outdatedness of curricula, insufficient real practice in production, and low adaptability of graduates to the labor market.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, by shaping the vocational education system in accordance with the needs of the labor market, it is possible to: ensure youth employment, reduce unemployment, provide the modern economy with competitive personnel, and increase the well-being of the population.

Therefore, ensuring the inextricable link between vocational education and the labor market is a priority direction not only of the education strategy, but also of the development of society as a whole.

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